

AI-Driven Dynamic Network Slicing Optimization leveraging Temporal Graph Networks

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Abstract—As 5th Generation (5G) and Beyond 5G (B5G) networks evolve, dynamic resource allocation and management is crucial for supporting the diversity of devices and the mixed traffic types. Network slicing enables the logical segmentation of an infrastructure to meet specific Quality of Service (QoS) requirements posed by applications, but factors such as fluctuating traffic, user mobility, and cross-slice interference, pose challenges towards a proactive resource allocation. Traditional methods struggle with these factors, leading to inefficiencies. Therefore, this paper explores the concept of AI-driven network performance prediction and resource allocation framework using Temporal Graph Networks (TGNs). By integrating TGN with the NS-3 simulator, the work in the paper demonstrates an efficient approach to predict throughput in a network. The proposed solution advances spatiotemporal Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques enabling more accurate network prediction and adaptive resource optimization, towards dynamic network slicing.

Index Terms—AI, slicing, NS-3, NS3-AI, TGN, throughput prediction.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE rapid of evolution of the 5th Generation (5G) and B5G networks, along with the growing demand for latency-critical applications such as autonomous systems, augmented reality (AR), and real-time industrial Internet of Things (IoT), has made the management of resources within a network, more critical than ever. As networks become increasingly complex and dynamic, traditional methods focusing on static allocation struggle to keep up with fluctuating demands. In this context, network slicing emerges as a key technology, enabling the logical partitioning of a physical infrastructure to provide tailored QoS guarantees. By allowing resources to be allocated based on specific application requirements, network slicing through Software Defined Networking (SDN) enhances efficiency and ensures optimal performance in shared and dynamic network environments [1]. However, the dynamic and heterogeneous nature of modern networks, characterized by fluctuating traffic loads, user mobility and spatially correlated interference among slices, poses significant challenges for efficient or even proactive resource allocation even through

slicing. For instance, in the context of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), large-scale experiments have revealed several operational challenges in automated 5G-enabled UAV flights, particularly concerning variations in 5G signal quality as the UAV moves between cells while airborne, resulting in multiple handovers and QoS degradation [2]. This challenge highlights the need for proactive resource allocation strategies, capable of predicting and subsequently adapting the network taking into account its dynamic conditions. Moreover, in the case of slices, cross-slice interference may arise leading to conflict of resources between slices, and the disruption of service isolation can directly impact QoS, causing degradation [3].

Traditional approaches towards prediction, such as threshold-based reactive scaling or statistical models like ARIMA [4] often lack the ability to adjust to network dynamics, leading to overprovisioning, Service Level Agreements (SLA) violations, or underutilization [3] of resources. To address these limitations, prediction of performance based on Artificial Intelligence (AI), has emerged as a critical enabler of intelligent, self-optimizing networks (SONs) [5]. Various machine learning approaches, including both deep learning and traditional methods (Random Forest). Furthermore, existing frameworks often rely on offline training, limiting their applicability to real-world scenarios where network conditions continuously evolve [6]. These gaps emphasize the need for spatiotemporal AI models which are capable of capturing both temporal trends and structural relationships especially in dynamic network environments.

The integration of Graphical Neural Networks (GNNs) with temporal attention mechanisms, represents a candidate solution to this challenge. Temporal Graph Networks (TGNs) dynamically model interactions between network entities, while at the same time preserving historical relevance [7]. Unlike Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) or Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), TGNs inherently support online learning, enabling continuous adaptation to real-time data streams, a critical requirement for mobile networks with rapidly changing topologies. Despite their theoretical promise, the application of TGNs to network slicing remains quite underexplored, particularly in adaptive systems where predictions directly influence resource allocation decisions.

On the other hand, the 5G System (5GS) supports advanced prediction mechanisms for notifications on potential QoS fluctuations within the network through Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) [8]. This is an essential function within the 5G system (5GS), which collects and analyses the data of the network to generate valuable insights and predictions that support decision-making processes. By interfacing with various network entities in both the 5G Core (5GC) and the

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5G Radio Access Network (RAN), NWDAF centralizes data collection and analysis, delivering real-time network analytics essential for potential QoS changes allowing to explore network behaviour more comprehensively and make proper adaptations.

In this work, we propose an AI-driven framework for network performance prediction that uses TGN model. By integrating TGN with the Network Simulation-3 (NS-3) simulator via the NS-3-AI shared memory interface, we establish a real-time feedback system (online training), where spatiotemporal congestion predictions subsequently lead to dynamic optimization of key network parameters, including Physical Resource Block (PRB) allocation and efficient management of slices within a 5G network using SDN. The real-time graph-based representation of the network, allows for efficient and precise prediction that can subsequently enhance decision-making by enabling more adaptive and priority aware resource allocation across different slices. The mechanism of dynamic resource allocation is also described. However, the main work in this paper is focusing on the predictions, which are validated through three scenarios in NS-3.

The structure of the paper is outlined as follows. Section II describes the proposed framework and the overall concept, while Section III delves towards the design details of the TGN model. Section IV presents the simulation setup and configurations used to evaluate the model, followed by Section V which analyses and discusses the outcomes of the simulation and finally Section VI concludes the paper.

II. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

The proposed architecture presented in Fig. 1 is built upon the work in [9] which describes the key characteristics of the core openness and the capabilities it provides in predicting QoS. Moving a step forward, the framework in this paper presents an architectural approach that integrates a 5G network implementation using the NS-3 simulation environment [10] enhanced by the capabilities of NS-3 AI for a data-driven approach [11]. As depicted in Fig.1 the rationale of this architecture maps to essential 5G core components such as Network Data Application Function (NWDAF) and radio access network (RAN) modules, thus reflecting a fully integrated 5G core network within the NS-3 environment. The core network is implemented through the Packet Gateway, *epcHelper* \rightarrow *GetPgwNode* (), enabling simulation of real-world networking behaviors with slicing capabilities.

The 5G RAN module is implemented through the 5G-LENA [12] which is an open-source module for the 5G New Radio (NR) that can be attached to NS-3 to simulate connectivity between base stations (gNBs) and user equipment (UE), accurately modeling the radio interface, signaling processes, and data exchange functionalities of a 5G network. A key feature of the framework is the network slicing implementation where the architecture takes into account multiple slices (e.g., voice, video, gaming, AR, UAV), designed to isolate and prioritize resources based on different QoS characteristics. To further enhance network intelligence and operational efficiency, the proposed framework incorporates the AI capabilities to map

Fig. 1. Proposed architecture for slicing prediction mechanism in a 5G network.

NWDAF functionality, and the AI / ML enablement services according to 3GPP to optimize network parameters, and improve overall service delivery [13].

In this context, NS-3 and NS-3 AI are utilized to achieve an efficient resource allocation across network slices (in the context of NS-3 this corresponds to increased bandwidth). The Dynamic Resource Allocation (DRA) framework is being performed via SDN related module. The main rationale is that the data generated during the scenarios, is fed to the AI models, which then predict the status of the network (throughput). The SDN, based on these predictions adapts its rules to make adjustments across the slices, according to a predefined priority order. It is also important to highlight that the paper focuses on TGN and its prediction accuracy for overall network throughput, enabling its use for per-slice throughput prediction. Two algorithms have been designed and implemented within NS-3 AI, and the LSTM model serves as the baseline to benchmark the efficacy of the TGN based approach.

III. DESIGN OF THE MODEL SCHEME

A. Temporal Graph Network Design

The proposed system aims to model the dynamic interactions within a 5G and B5G network environment. By leveraging TGN, the system can capture and predict the interactions and dependencies among the nodes over time, considering the mobility of UEs, as well as the network's evolving topology. The TGN model uses memory-enhanced temporal graph learning for dynamic throughput prediction. It captures time-evolving states of the network, including congestion levels at gNBs, traffic demand of UEs, and the uplink radio channel of the devices with the gNBs. The TGN processes the data structured as a graph $G = (N, E)$, where N stands for nodes and E represents the edges. The nodes correspond to network entities such as UEs, gNBs, while edges represent data flows or signaling interactions. The weights of these edges reflect the time difference between consecutive events. Each node is characterized by 4 key inputs: CQI, latency (in seconds), packet loss and uplink throughput (in Mbps). The model processes dynamic network states through a sequence of graph snapshots, where each node represents a network element (UE or gNB) with associated features. The temporal dynamics are captured through the model's recurrent architecture that

processes these graph snapshots over time. The graph structure adapts to the number of active network elements presented in each scenario, with node features encoding the current network state. The proposed TGN model approach consists of the following main variables:

- Memory Module: Stores temporal features of previous network states
- Graph Embedding Layer: Captures spatial dependencies among UEs, gNBs
- Temporal Embedding Layer: Processes time-dependent interactions between nodes
- Prediction Head: expected latency, and throughput of the network

The TGN was configured with an embedding dimension of 64 to efficiently capture temporal dependencies. The model was trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 and a batch size of 32, to ensure both stability and speed, while Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss was employed for optimization over 100 epochs.

B. Dynamic Resource Allocation Mechanism

The DRA mechanism, involves real-time adaptation of network resources based on QoS requirements, throughput levels, and AI-based predictions stemming from TGN. The overall goal is to optimize network slicing and ensure high-priority slices, (e.g. the UAV slice), receive guaranteed resources while dynamically adjusting the allocation for other slices, based on provided SLAs. In this sense, SDN's centralized controller manages the network topology and enforces slices' allocations as follows:

- Input: TGN predictions (throughput $T_s(t+1)$) and real time network state ($Cr(t), G(t)$)
- Flow rules to allocate $x_{s,r}(t)$ across gNBs and UEs

The mathematical framework for handling slicing allocation in proactive actions of the SDN can be defined as follows.

- Slices: $S = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_N\}$ where N is the number of slices (UAV, gaming, video, voice, AR)
- Resources: $R = \{R_1, R_2, \dots, R_M\}$ (PRBs, bandwidth), where M is the number of resource types (bandwidth, PRBs, at edge nodes)
- Network Entities: Nodes and edges in a graph $G(t) = \{E(t), N(t)\}$, updated dynamically over time t as per TGN
- Resource Allocation: $x_{s,R}(t)$, the amount of resource r allocated to slice s at time t .
- Utility Function: $U_s(x_s(t))$, the utility of slice s based on its allocated resources $x_s(t) = \{x_{s,r_1}(t), \dots, x_{s,R_M}(t)\}$
- Total Resource Capacity: $C_R(t)$, the available capacity of resource R at time t

The optimization problem can be expressed as

$$\max U(t) = \sum_{s \in S} w_s U_s(x_s(t)) \quad (1)$$

where w_s is the weight reflecting the priority of slice s (higher for UAV URLLC slices in our case). Each slice has a defined utility function that quantifies its performance based

Fig. 2. The online training architecture of NS-3 and NS3-AI with TGN model.

on these parameters, enabling optimized resource allocation and adaptive network management. The utility function for each slice is provided in equation (2).

$$U_s(x_s(t)) = \alpha_s T_s(x_s(t)) - \beta_s L_s(x_s(t)) + \gamma_s R'_s(x_s(t)) \quad (2)$$

where α_s , β_s , and γ_s are weights reflecting the slice's sensitivity to throughput (T_s), latency (L_s), and reliability (packet delivery ratio, R'_s), respectively. For instance, a predicted throughput drop for the UAV slice increases latency sensitivity (β_s high), causing subsequent PRB allocations and higher bandwidth (γ_s high). These parameters can be dynamically adjusted based on TGN predictions of throughput.

IV. SIMULATION SETUP

In the proposed setup, the use of real-time online training, was deemed appropriate. In such a case the system continuously monitors key network performance metrics, including UL throughput, latency, Channel Quality Indicator (CQI) and packet loss, that are used for training and execution of the model. The NS3-AI framework integrates the NS-3 network simulator with AI models using a shared memory interface, enabling real-time decision-making. During the simulation, spatiotemporal data is continuously exchanged between NS-3 and the AI model, which processes the information and provides adaptive control decisions. These decisions are then fed back into the simulation, enabling dynamic adjustments of resource allocations. The overall architecture of the framework is illustrated in Fig.2.

By implementing both AI models (LSTM/TGN) within NS3-AI using PyTorch Geometric core learning library, the system predicts future network conditions in real-time, enabling proactive estimation of the throughput. Based on these estimations, network resources are dynamically allocated to the different slices (video, AR, gaming, voice, UAVs). In case of throughput degradation and violation of SLAs, the system dynamically reallocates PRBs to prioritize the slices, ensuring

critical operations remain unaffected. This process operates within a continuous feedback loop, where network conditions are reassessed every second based on the latest AI-driven predictions, through the shared memory.

To assess and validate the proposed approach, three different scenarios have been applied and tested, each representing varying levels of network density and mobility. In the first scenario, a small number of UEs are connected to a single gNB, ensuring stable connectivity due to its constant position. This setup serves as a baseline for evaluating network performance in a controlled environment. In the second scenario, the introduction of additional gNBs and drones increases network complexity and dynamic mobility with models applied to UEs and drones. In this setup the presence of multiple gNBs allows for better load distribution, increased congestion and improving network efficiency. The third case represents the most complex and high-density environment, featuring 50 UEs including 2 drones, employing the Random walk and Gauss-Markov mobility models respectively. This mobility model along with the density results in significant link variations targeting to test the system's ability to manage resource allocation and network slicing.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF THE EVALUATED SCENARIOS

Parameters	Sc.1	Sc.2	Sc.3
Number of UEs	7	15	50
Number of gNBs	1	3	5
Simulation time	10 s	10 s	10 s
Data rate	200 Mbps	200 Mbps	200 Mbps
Mobility model (UEs)	Const position	Random walk	Random walk
Mobility model (UAVs)	n/a	Gauss-Markov	Gauss-Markov
Transport Protocol	UDP	UDP	UDP
Flow Monitoring	Enabled	Enabled	Enabled

This setup must efficiently distribute resources among a large number of devices with differing communication needs, including low-latency, high-reliability connections for drones. The dynamic nature of this scenario tests the system's ability to handle congestion and optimization of resource accordingly. By evaluating these three scenarios, we analyze the impact of mobility, density, and dynamic network infrastructure on overall performance, providing key insights on how the TGN model is suitable to learn patterns and capture the temporal dynamics. The predictions then will be applied to the system so as to optimize the resources on the different slices accordingly.

V. EVALUATION OF RESULTS

This chapter presents the results of the AI-driven prediction framework, implemented in NS-3 and NS3-AI. The proposed TGN model is compared against a baseline LSTM model and evaluated under different network conditions, as described in the different scenarios. Specifically, the effectiveness of the model in predicting network throughput is evaluated against the LSTM baseline.

Initially, Fig. 3 compares actual throughput values with predictions from the two models: LSTM and TGN in Sc1. In this simple baseline scenario, the TGN captures the general trend of predictions, with its output closely matching the real

Fig. 3. LSTM and TGN throughput prediction vs actual values in Sc.1.

Fig. 4. LSTM and TGN throughput prediction vs actual values in Sc.2.

throughput values, however, some notable spikes are identified likely due to Sc.1 static nodes' configuration, resulting in insufficient structural updates of TGN. Likewise, the LSTM model exhibits more noticeable deviations from actual values, likely stemming from inherent limitations in LSTM's sequential processing architecture, which struggles to fully capture complex, non-linear patterns present in the throughput data of the simulation. Therefore, considering the smoothness and stability of its predictions, the TGN model appears to perform marginally better in capturing the general throughput behavior in this particular instance.

Fig. 4 presents the results for the second scenario. In this case, while both TGN and LSTM capture the overall throughput trend, their performance diverges significantly during network events. The TGN maintains better stability during throughput spikes and drops, with prediction errors remaining consistent over the observation period. This consistency suggests that the graph-based architecture successfully captures both temporal patterns and structural relationships between the nodes of the network. In the third scenario, as shown in Fig. 5, the TGN model continues to predict better than LSTM model maintaining better predictive accuracy and stability. The stability also suggests that TGN model is better at adapting to rapid changes in network conditions and highlights its ability to model and predict well even in complex and dynamic scenarios including a large number of nodes and mobility patterns. The LSTM reveals some noticeable spikes (e.g. indices 20-60) suggesting that the model struggles with sudden

Fig. 5. . LSTM and TGN throughput prediction vs actual values in Sc.3.

changes in the traffic of the network, and the complexity of the scenario. The results are further supported by the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) values collected for each scenario. In Sc.1, TGN achieves an MAE of 3.7 compared to 4.4 for LSTM. For Sc.2, TGN's MAE is 0.6 compared to 0.9 for LSTM, and in Sc.3, TGN records 0.5 while LSTM 0.9.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an AI-driven framework for network performance prediction for slicing resource optimization using TGN model. By integrating TGN model, the proposed system enables real-time, spatiotemporal modeling of dynamic network conditions, improving slicing efficiency and decision-making in resource allocation. The evaluation across three different scenarios demonstrated the prediction accuracy of the TGN model that has a consistent behavior in both simple and complex network conditions compared to LSTM. These findings highlight the potential of integrating graph-based learning models in 5G and B5G networks, thus facilitating more intelligent and efficient management. The next steps of this research will utilize SDN principles to implement the network slicing and optimize the allocation of resources, based on the predictions stemming from the TGN model.

VII. REFERENCES

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